
| RESEARCH ARTICLE

Comparison Of Adiponectin and Atherogenic Risk Indices in Metabolically Healthy Obese and Normal Weight Individuals In Owerri, Nigeria

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| ABSTRACT

A subphenotype of obesity defined as “metabolically healthy” due to the presence of favourable risk factors, seems to be a misnomer and may be misleading, especially in an obesogenic environment like Owerri, with a traditional perception of metabolically healthy obesity as a sign of wellness and prosperity. This research seeks to compare some metabolic profiles of metabolically healthy obese (MHO) and metabolically healthy normal weight (MHNW) individuals to underscore the metabolic healthiness of the MHO.

Aim: The assess the extent of the healthiness of MHO by comparing some metabolic profiles of MHO and MHNW.

Methods: A total of 130 enrollees (60 MHO and 70 MHNW) aged between 25 and 60 years participated in this study. Fasting lipid profile and adiponectin were analyzed using standard laboratory techniques while atherogenic risk indices (CRI-1, CRI-2 and AIP) were mathematically determined.

Results: Significant lower adiponectin and HDL were observed in MHO compared to MHNW ($p < 0.05$). Conversely, other lipid fractions and artherogenic indices were statistically higher in MHO than MHNW ($p < 0.05$). In MHO, no significant correlation was observed between adiponectin and (BMI, lipid fractions, lipid indices), however, moderate positive correlations were observed between systolic blood pressure and BMI ($r = .282, p = 0.029$), TC ($r = .298, p = 0.024$), LDL ($r = .298, p = 0.021$), CRI-1 ($r = .257, p = 0.047$), CRI-2 ($r = .268, p = 0.038$). Additionally, strong positive and negative correlations were found between some lipid fractions and lipid indices.

Conclusion: The findings of this study shows that the MHO is not as safe as defined but ticks towards unfavourable profile.